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The linguistic frontier Spanish/English in Gibraltar

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1. Overview

This chapter presents the bilingual situation of the British overseas territory of Gibraltar and the structural evolution of its local variety of code-switching across different generations. We studied code-switching at the community level from a sociolinguistic perspective, considering Gibraltar as a dynamic space that has undergone many historical and sociopolitical changes that are directly reflected in linguistic changes across generations. Through the sociolinguistic analysis of code-switching patterns, we confirmed that different age groups have preferences for particular types of bilingual patterns.

For the purpose of our analysis, we combined two oral corpora, the FR-Corpus¹ (2012) and the RG-Corpus² (2020/21), to study generational variation in the local variety of code-switching in Gibraltar known as Yanito. The combination of the two corpora allowed a better and deeper comparison of several generations of speakers, making it possible to track linguistic changes (shifts). Several examples will be presented to illustrate the use of different code-switching patterns across four generations of speakers.

This study thus aims to present how Yanito (structurally) functions in different generations of Gibraltarians by reflecting on and describing how the linguistic code has evolved in relation to societal transformations and how it stands out as a representation of a local identity. We observed that Yanito is described by speakers as a distinctive code with an important identity value, and we located it as the center of a *linguistic continuum* in the community of Gibraltar.

Based on the observations, we consider the study of Gibraltar and its local variety of code-switching important for current research on language shifts and contact linguistics (English–Spanish).

¹ FR-Corpus (more in the methodology section): This corpus consists of 17 interviews, 16 semiguided group interviews with pupils from Gibraltar's two secondary schools, 36 everyday conversations, five telephone conversations, one radio interview, five recordings from a Spanish class, one speech at a primary school, and 13 conversations without participant observation. The interviews with adults are one-to-one interviews with a short questionnaire that covers basic information and questions about life and growing up in Gibraltar. As the conversations evolve and become more informal, they become more of a lively discussion rather than a stiff interview. The interviews at schools were conducted with three to five pupils and divided into three parts: first, the interviewer and interviewee got to know each other and the interviewer gathered background information; in the second there were cards with prompts on them in both languages, like "best holiday experience / mejores vacaciones," so the pupils could decide which language to react in; and the third part consisted of commenting on pictures that presented typical English, Spanish, and Gibraltarian subjects. The daily conversations took place in familiar surroundings, e.g., while shopping at a grocery store or sitting in a cafe. The most valuable recordings are the ones that were conducted without participant observation, where informants took a recording device with them and documented the most natural speech.

² RG-Corpus (more in the methodology section): The main corpus consists of 15 focus groups of three people (exceptionally, four)—who knew each other very well—for a total of 46 participants. The participants in these focus groups engaged in a natural, semiguided conversation thanks to a conversation guide that elicited information on different topics and exposed participants to various levels of formality throughout the conversation. The focus groups were divided into three age groups: A (ages 16–21), B (ages 22–28) and C (ages 29–35). There were also three additional mixed groups: BA1, AB2, and BC3. Females and males were almost equally represented. The focus groups were conducted using an online methodology and the well-known tool Zoom, which made it possible to avoid the presence of the interviewer and created a natural atmosphere, with the exception of the A focus groups, which were conducted in public schools after the relaxation of COVID-19 measures. The examples presented in this article were extracted from a first sample of the corpus consisting of six semidirected focus groups (RG-Corpus) and 10 previously conducted single semidirected interviews on languages and culture in Gibraltar.

2. The Gibraltarian frontier

Gibraltar is a small territory at the tip of the Iberian Peninsula. It is only 6.5 square kilometers wide and home to 33,691 inhabitants (World Bank 2020). Despite its size, the territory is rich in ethnicities, traditions, religions, cultures, and languages, and its sovereignty continues to be a matter of dispute between Spain and Britain. Since 1704, when an English-Dutch fleet grabbed the Rock and put it under the British flag with the signing of the Treaty of Utrecht, Gibraltar has been a place defined both by its sovereign, Britain, and its neighbor, Spain. The disagreement over its sovereignty is reflected in a border that has witnessed close relations between the citizens on both sides but also differences, making it a symbol of contact between countries, cultures, and languages. Various sociopolitical and historical factors, of which we will only list a few, make the Gibraltar border and the territory itself a place of considerable sociolinguistic interest.

Before and some years after the cession of the territory to British hands as an end of the War of Spanish Succession (1713), the border was completely open and under no regulation, so there was a strong relationship between the territory of Gibraltar and the neighboring territories in Spain known as *El Campo de Gibraltar* (meaning “the Gibraltar countryside”). Different ethnic groups have settled on and around the Rock, bringing with them their cultures, traditions, and languages, including Italian, Maltese, French, Arabic, Hebrew, and Portuguese. Languages have emerged, mixed, and influenced each other. The path to an “anglicization” (Archer 2006: 108) has extended over three centuries. After the invasion, the British garrison was forced to communicate with the locals and people from the hinterland in Spanish. Until the Second World War, Spanish was not only used as the lingua franca (Levey 2006: 78) but was also the language “of the hearth and the cradle and of the social domain as a whole” (Archer 2006: 110). English, on the other hand, which was solely used for written communication (Kramer 1998: 312), interacted with the local language and finally went through a process of “nativisation” and “normalisation” (Kellermann 2001: 285).

Several historical factors are decisive for understanding the changes in the relations between Spain, Great Britain, and Gibraltar and the transformation of Gibraltar’s society and linguistic situation. First, the outbreak of the Spanish Civil War in 1936 and the danger of a hostile takeover led to a reinforcement of the military and the border, which was reflected in an increase of English-speaking soldiers stationed on the Rock and a need for civilians to emphasize their British character. Second, the Second World War and the evacuation of the Gibraltarian population to England, Jamaica, Madeira, and Northern Ireland reinforced their feeling of belonging to Britain and confronted evacuated civilians with the English language and British culture. The urgency to foster British culture and the English language in the territory led to the establishment of a new national curriculum in the Gibraltarian school system with English as a teaching tool. Finally, the climax of anglicization came with the third and most important political factor: the closure of the border between Spain and Gibraltar from 1969 to 1982. Especially after the end of the war, Spain’s desire to recover the territory increased and the British government responded with several cultural and linguistic initiatives, which were reflected in a series of changes in Gibraltar’s political and educational landscape that promoted the emergence of a sense of Gibraltar’s own identity. These efforts were redoubled after the Spanish government’s response to a referendum in 1967 where almost 100 percent of the Gibraltarian population decided “voluntarily to retain their link with Britain” (*Second Red Book*, Document 118, 756). Spain immediately mandated the complete closure of the border for people and transport between 1969 and 1982, which resulted in isolation from the Spanish mainland. There was no more direct contact with Spain; economic connections were cut; Spanish media and recreational opportunities in Spain vanished from Gibraltarian everyday life and were replaced by English ones. Moreover, an anti-Spanish attitude developed (Haller 2000: 155).

Gibraltar's search for their own identity was shaken and reinforced after their separation from home, family, and friends during World War II, after realizing that being legally British was still different from being British and after the need for self-sufficiency caused by the closure of the border. The Gibraltar population withstood this crisis caused by a shortage of workers and a lack of products and materials with the help of London, and the territory came out of it stronger and more autonomous than ever. In 1983, under the Immigration Act of 1981 (Gold 1994 in Canessa 2019: 208), Gibraltar's became full British citizens, and the population took control of the enclave after a reduction of the colonial hierarchy and military presence. Gibraltar's built up their identity as explicitly British, as opposed to Spanish, in order to ensure international protection.

After that, Gibraltar's identity continued to evolve and was confronted with entry into the European Union (EU) and the phenomenon of globalization. The opening of the border in 1982 also entailed an opening to the EU with all its benefits. The relationship between the Spanish and Gibraltar's was reinvigorated by a porous border, which thousands of Spanish workers began to cross daily to work in Gibraltar, while hundreds of Gibraltar's took the opportunity to visit family, go shopping, travel, or even own a home in the neighboring country. Gibraltar's economy thrived, and it became a European hub for financial services and online gaming (*New York Times*). The feeling of being European and part of the EU contributed to the recognition of Gibraltar as a unique territory and the formation of its identity. The English language continued to strengthen its position as a language of globalization and the increase in tourists and workers from non-European countries added to the continuing importance of English in Gibraltar's society. At the same time, the porous border meant that Gibraltar's came in contact with Spanish workers and neighbors, and this ensured that the Spanish language continued to be heard on the streets of Gibraltar. The Gibraltar's government started to show interest in a bilingual Gibraltar, and the educational curriculum changed to include instruction in Spanish to adapt to the historical and border situation of Gibraltar. Furthermore, the EU and closer relations between the Spanish government and Gibraltar made it possible to open an Instituto Cervantes between 2011 and 2015, allowing thousands of students to improve their Spanish skills and proficiency in fully booked courses.

When the question of Brexit arose, Gibraltar wanted to remain in the EU, as expressed by almost 96 percent of the people of Gibraltar in a 2016 referendum. Despite Gibraltar's opposition, the implementation of Brexit forced Gibraltar to leave the common European area. The border, which had always played a central role in the development of a Gibraltar's national identity, became the sticking point in Brexit negotiations between Madrid, London, and Gibraltar. Given the difficulty of reaching an agreement, Gibraltar's shuddered at the possibility of a new closure or greater control at the border. A last-minute deal between the UK and Spain allowed for free movement between the British overseas territory and European countries, included Gibraltar in Schengen, and left control of the border in the hands of the EU's Frontex agency. The impact of this decision on the linguistic and cultural landscape, as well as on the Gibraltar's identity, is still unknown. This moment in history brings back memories of the "no barriers" between people from La Línea and people from Gibraltar and shows a glimmer of hope in international politics: "We believe that we may now be able to reset our relationship with Spain and cast it in a more positive light" (Fabian Picardo, prime minister of Gibraltar, *The New York Times*). On the other hand, Gibraltar's are still striving to show the world their distinctive social and cultural identity and to differentiate themselves both from Spain, despite their geographical proximity, and from Britain, despite their political status. In this process of political and social changes and with the border more porous than ever, languages and local culture are once again playing a fundamental role in the development of Gibraltar's identity. In the search for a firmly consolidated community and their own identity, languages are playing

a crucial role: both British English and Castellano, or rather Gibraltarian English and Gibraltarian Spanish, as well as the local variety of code-switching, Yanito.³

3. Yanito at the core of the linguistic continuum in Gibraltar

Gibraltar’s linguistic repertoire is both fascinating and complex, for it is not confined to the delimited use of English and Spanish. Instead, these languages have developed in coexistence, resulting in several interferences that shape Gibraltarian English and Spanish (briefly documented by Escoriza Morera and Díaz Domingo 2008; Goría 2018; Kellermann 2001; Moyer 2013). The mix of both languages constitutes the basis of the local variety of code-switching, Yanito, which has long been described as the Spanish dialect spoken in Gibraltar. Yanito is characterized by the insertion of English words and phrases within an otherwise Spanish discourse and has been influenced by other Mediterranean languages (Kellermann 2001). It is common to hear speakers from older Gibraltarian generations, like Alice in Example (1) (RG-Corpus), describe what they speak as “not-proper” Spanish.

- (1) ALICE: We don’t speak proper Spanish, we speak Yanito. Yanito is our own language, and it is not just a mix of Spanish and English, we have our own words.

However, this local variety has been exposed to the sociolinguistic changes in Gibraltar over time. From an extended diglossia with British English as the “high variety” and Andalusian Spanish as the “low variety”, the local linguistic situation has developed into what could be better described as dilalia. This means that the structural and functional separation between the official language and the local varieties, as well as the domains and specific pragmatic functions for each, are no longer as clear as they were. The linguistic situation in Gibraltar is marked by intermediate variants between standard and dialectal varieties, and speakers shift from a dialectal variant to a standard one to adapt to a situation. This dilalic constellation can be summarized as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: The dilalic linguistic relation in Gibraltar (Feijóo Rodríguez 2018: 67; adapted from Krefeld 2004: 35).

This diagram shows that the “high variety”, English, is not merely used in formal settings anymore but has also extended into new domains and transformed Yanito. Shifts in dilalic contexts can be encouraged by several factors such as the relationship between speakers, the formality of the speech event, the topic of the conversation, and the medium (Auer 2005, 2013). In fact, in Gibraltar, the “high variety”, English, has recently been overlapping with the “low varieties”, Spanish and Yanito, in many of their functional domains. This situation differs from a diglossic one, as the “high variety” is also being used in daily speech, which means that

³ Both *Yanito* and *Llanito* refer to the local variety of speech in Gibraltar. The origin of the term is not clear. One hypothesis is that it comes from the English word *Johnny*, as many British soldiers were called that way. Another assumption is that it originated from the Italian name *Gianni*, due to the many Genoese immigrants in Gibraltar. And the third hypothesis is that it derives from the Spanish word *llano*, which describes the area around the Rock (see Kellerman 2001: 8). In this chapter we decided to use the form with *y* instead of *ll*.

it occurs in both formal and informal settings, while the “low varieties” are only being used informally or for specific purposes. This means that all the varieties are applied not only in parallel but also in alternation. In 2001, Kellermann already noticed that “English is becoming increasingly common in the home and with friends” (2001: 278). Levey confirmed this: “Findings showed that a significant and ever-increasing number of young Gibraltarians feel more comfortable speaking English in home and school environments” (2008: 165). And we also observed an increase of Yanito for social purposes. For instance, it is used in greetings at the beginning of educational events or during breaks between official meetings as well as among teachers in schools.

Thus, as Errico first argued, the situation in Gibraltar should be studied as a linguistic continuum (1997: 49; cited in Alameda Hernández 2006: 49), in which Yanito forms the center. Errico placed the two standard varieties, British English and Spanish, at each end of the continuum. These are then followed by the local varieties of Gibraltar English and Gibraltar Spanish toward the center, which is Yanito:

Figure 2: The linguistic continuum in Gibraltar (Feijóo Rodríguez 2018: 64).

As the center of the linguistic continuum and as a result of mingling between local English and Spanish, Yanito is a useful mixing code with several functions for speakers. We reflect on this functionality and speakers’ own opinions about this local variety with the help of examples extracted from both corpora. As the speakers in the example below mention, Yanito is not considered a language, neither outside nor inside the community, but it serves community purposes and is considered a widely spoken and useful dialect. The usefulness of Yanito gives this variety a certain prestige that allows for the debate between three schoolteachers in Example (2) (RG-Corpus).

- (2) JOHN: Would you say Yanito is a language?
 MICKEY: Not a language, dialect.
 JOHN: *No sé quillo, pero después tú vas y es un rollo todo el mundo habla así.*
 NICHOLAS: *Sí pero* it’s not a language in itself, it’s a dialect.

Furthermore, Yanito has also become a symbol of identity and a way to identify people from Gibraltar, both inside and outside the community. Despite being mostly used in informal settings, this local code-switching variety is gaining a certain covert prestige among speakers as the language for socializing and exhibiting some attributions related to Gibraltar people, such as being different, confident, and friendly, as shown in Example (3) (RG-Corpus).

- (3) MELANIE: If you live in Gibraltar, you are probably Yanito, to be honest. Because, you know what Yanito is, like you mix words. Yanito is like you mix Spanish and you mix English together in one language and the way you act, as well. It’s like different, confident maybe, very friendly with people.

Several speakers, like Claire in Example (4) (RG-Corpus), noted the ease of using both languages, of expressing yourself in both languages, and of being able to communicate with everyone as something very positive. Yanito therefore serves as a useful tool for national and binational communication.

- (4) CLAIRES: *En Yanito, si vamos lo que te viene a la cabeza, por ejemplo, if I can describe myself easier in English I will speak English y sino pues I will speak in Spanish, ¿sabes lo que digo? Lo que pasa que si no eres de aquí, pues te coge un poquito fuera de juego, ¿no? Es un lenguaje bueno de saber y aquí vienen mucho trabajadores españoles y hay que trabajar y convivir.*

Yanito is thus gaining importance as the community's local variety of speech and as a symbol of identity; it is not just a case of code-switching, as Jonas states in Example (5) (RG-Corpus).

- (5) JONAS: *El Yanito es mucho más que un simple code-switching, no es solo el inglés y el español. Hay palabras en Yanito que vienen de otras lenguas, o sea del genovés, o del italiano o del maltés.*

It also serves as a mechanism for making Gibraltar different from Spain and the UK, while reflecting the coexistence of former languages and cultures. However, members of older generations—like Paco in Example (6) and Aidan in Example (7) (FR-Corpus)—have noted a loss or ongoing disappearance of many of the distinctive features of this variety and point to a disappearance of the role of Spanish in the younger Gibraltarian generations.

- (6) PACO: *Mucha gente el español lo han perdido. [...] Además de eso es una cosa que se está perdiendo. Y eso había que tener un record porque muchas de las palabras que yo tengo ahí [en el diccionario Yanito] yo nunca las usé. Y se han acabado de usar porque se inventaron por necesidad. Cuando teníamos al arsenal que había muchos españoles trabajando y habían ingleses mandando y ni uno se entendía ni el otro y las palabras se [...] corrompían. ¿Qué quiere decir? Que había que inventarse por el sonido de la palabra que es lo que quería decir. Y claro, al [...] no haber ya esa mano de obra española pues eso se fue perdiendo. Ya hablamos inglés, ya hablamos inglés, ya no había necesidad de inventar ni [...] palabras. Los niños tampoco lo usan. [...] Los jóvenes usan más Spanglish. El Spanglish lo entienden los que hablan inglés y español. La idea del Yanito es que no lo entienden ni uno ni el otro [...]. Por ejemplo, si yo le digo a un inglés [...] “stop giving me the tin” = no me des la lata. O “because of the flies” = por si las moscas.*

- (7) AIDAN: *Pero ahora creo que hemos ido full circle como se dice en inglés, ¿no? Que quizás nuestros hijos hablan demasiado el inglés y la tendencia es que prácticamente no te hablan en español.*

Based on the previous examples and remarks, we can state that even though younger generations still claim to use Yanito with friends and value it as an important code for social and identity purposes, older generations do not identify younger speakers as speakers of Yanito. This could be explained by the loss of Spanish in younger generations and the ongoing process of a language shift within the community. We observed that this local variety has undergone significant structural changes that make it difficult for speakers to consider it Yanito and for researchers to define it. Furthermore, this local variety varies greatly between individuals and groups of people. The fact is that this local code has a complex function in different generations, especially with regard to the combination of English and Spanish elements, and requires special attention.

4. Redefining Yanito from a code-switching perspective

In this section of the chapter, we offer a different view of Yanito by describing the structural changes that this local variety has undergone. For the purpose of studying the structures of code-switching in Yanito observed in two oral corpora, we used Muysken's (2000; 2013) theoretical background on code-switching strategies. Due to the lack of space and the

focus of this volume, we have limited ourselves to analyzing the structural changes over generations and to commenting on the frequency of certain code-switching mechanisms in spontaneous or semidirected natural group conversations. However, we understand that this issue is closely related to other sociolinguistic and discursive aspects that we would like to address in more detail at another time, namely, participant roles and relationships, participants' identities, language attitudes and perception, and communicative and interactional purposes. Even though we do not address those factors here, we considered them in the constitution of our corpora and may briefly refer to some of them during the study. Furthermore, it would also be possible to address the representation of Yanito within different environments (such as in different media, the linguistic landscape, education, etc.) to contrast our observations. Despite the need to summarize and concretize, we believe that the following analysis can provide a good overview of the actual situation of Yanito and of the importance of studying code-switching and mixed varieties based on flexible theoretical frameworks with sociolinguistic approaches that allow for better observation of the internal structure and of the relationship between internal evolution and the sociohistorical and political context.

The examples presented in this chapter are extracted from two different oral corpora that we refer to as the FR-Corpus and the RG-Corpus. The first data collected by Feijóo Rodríguez in 2012 encompasses interviews, focus groups, everyday conversations, and long-term recordings of three generations in Gibraltar. For this article we only used conversations from generation I and II, all of which were without participant observation, except for in the case of Example (14), which is from an interview. These everyday conversations were in groups of at least two and up to five participants and were literally without an interviewer, which means that they were, strictly speaking, not guided and reflect natural speech. The second corpus by Rodríguez García was collected between 2020 and 2021 and consists of, first, semidirected single interviews on the linguistic and cultural landscape and, second, natural and semidirected focus groups of young adults in Gibraltar with no intervention from the interviewer. This second corpus was used to exemplify the third and fourth generations of speakers. By combining these two corpora, we were able to study the evolution of Yanito in four complete generations of speakers and to analyze in closer detail how a language shift is affecting the structures of code-switching in Gibraltar. The four generations in our corpus were divided by age or year of birth as follows: the first generation was born between 1935 and 1951, the second generation between 1952 and 1982, the third generation between 1983 and 2000, and the fourth generation were born after the year 2000. The combination of two corpora is innovative and necessary for studying the evolution of Gibraltarian speech. In fact, authors like Weston (2012) and Goría (2020) have pointed toward the importance of studying language shifts and the evolution of bilingual speech across different generations of speakers in Gibraltar by analyzing how different code-switching strategies are representative of the bilingual speech of different generations and how bilingual lexical and grammatical items, such as discourse markers, are syntactically integrated in the discourse of different generations of speakers.

In this section, we describe the structural changes we identified, where the code-switching local variety appeared, and how it reflects the process of a language shift and change. As already mentioned, we used the code-switching strategies defined by Muysken (2000, 2013). His grammatical characterization of code-switching describes the following three strategies (2000: 3):

- *insertion* of material (lexical items or entire constituents) from one language (B) into a structure from the other language (A);
- *alternation* between structures from languages A and B; and
- *congruent lexicalization* of material from different lexical inventories into a shared grammatical structure combining languages A and B.

In 2013, Muysken extended this tripartite taxonomy by adding a fourth code-switching strategy: *backflagging*, which he describes as “the insertion of heritage language discourse markers in L2 discourse” (Muysken 2013: 713). The original matrix language (L1), or language A, of a speech community becomes the L2, or language B, for some speakers. This speech “is marked with flagging elements from the original community language” (Muysken 2013: 713). Typically, backflagging occurs outside a clause and only affects single units. This strategy is used especially frequently in Yanito and carries, as Muysken states, a clear ethnic connotation. All four strategies constituted our theoretical background for this chapter, as did Muysken’s consideration of the sociopolitical factors favoring these different strategies:

Factors	Strategies	Outcomes
Unequal power, (post)colonial settings, low proficiency	L1	Insertion
Political competition, high bilingual proficiency	UP ⁴	Alternation
Relaxed language norms, closely knit network, high bilingual proficiency, little typological and/or lexical distance, long contact	L1/L2	Congruent lexicalization
Shift in second or third generation	L2	Backflagging

Table 1: Sociopolitical factors and code-switching strategies (Muysken 2013: 720).

Based on these factors, we expected to find different strategies in different generations in Gibraltar: from single insertions of English in an otherwise Spanish clause in older generations to alternation and congruent lexicalization in bilingual adults and backflagging in younger generations. One factor that leads to backflagging is the shift from L1 to L2 (and consequently L2 to L1) in younger generations. This means they use the former L2 as their new L1. Even though Gibraltar does not represent a classic migratory situation in a postcolonial setting, it is similar to one. The socialization of the different generations is so disparate that generations III and IV (born after 1982) interact differently with Spanish and English than their parents and grandparents do. Hence, Muysken’s typology is particularly suitable for analyzing the data and describing the current language shift between the different generations. In the following, we analyze the different strategies in representative examples of the four different generations.

4.1 Insertion

There are manifold instances of typical insertions of English lexical items into a Spanish frame by generations I and II, as shown in the following examples. Example (8) demonstrates typical English lexical insertions associated with norms and rules, which are usually conducted in the official language, English; in Example (9), the insertions are associated with work and timetables, in this case related to school.

(8) FR-Corpus: generation I

JOE: *Y me dice no porque aquí no debe de aparcar escúchame el **parking** de ustedes es donde está el **barrier** de la puertecita que tenéis para dentro sí vale los de aquí ustedes no tenéis que venir para nada*

PACO: *es para nosotros para todos*

JOE: *vale no ustedes tenéis **access** pero no tenéis **parking** digo que dice usted usted quién es quién es éste quién es*

PACO: *quién era quién era ese.*

⁴ Universal principle (UP).

Single English constituents like *parking*, *barrier*, and *access* are inserted into a Spanish frame and nested with an a-b-a structure. The same can be observed for generation II, where single English elements such as *year eight*, *page*, or *on Mondays* are embedded in a Spanish structure, as in Example (9).

- (9) FR-Corpus: generation II
 PIE: Emily *tú cuándo tienes* **year eight**
 EMILY: *mejor mirarlo en la* **page**
 PIE: *ah ésta es la* **page**
 EMILY: *el* **year eight** *es aquí*
 PIE: *ah viernes y el otro*
 EMILY: *mira* **on Mondays**
 PIE: *ah* **Mondays** *qué te cae todo el* **Monday** *y* **Tuesday**
 EMILY: *sí*

The third generation exhibits these insertions as well, if not as frequently as the previous generations. Here again, the lexicon related to school, jobs, or institutions appears in English. However, in the younger speakers from generation III, we see a higher degree of individual variation. While some speakers, such as John and Mickey in Example (10), seem to feel more comfortable using Spanish as the matrix language of the clause and inserting the English elements, Nicholas replies in English when addressing a school topic.

- (10) RG-Corpus: generation III
 JOHN: *con Mickey me acuerdo que tu eras* **green** *y estábamos en* **maths** *juntos pero no me acuerdo verte en el* **classroom**
 MICKEY: *no porque tú te sentabas adelante con Jack y yo estaba atrás*
 JOHN: *yo estaba con Jack*
 MICKEY: *tú estabas adelante con Jack en* **year eight**
 JOHN: *y supongo que contigo*
 NICHOLAS: and with me

Examples of English insertions in a Spanish utterance can also be observed in speakers from the third and fourth generations, for instance, in the case of local celebrations and holidays, as in Example (11). Most of the time, however, the definite and indefinite articles are also expressed in English, as in the case of *a bank holiday*. In the fourth generation, we see that English constitutes the main language of interaction and the matrix language. Sometimes, Spanish segments are embedded in English discourse, and the insertion of English lexical items is then found within these embedded Spanish utterances.

- (11) RG-Corpus: generation IV
 NOLAN: this weekend I'm going to go to Spain with my familiy to *Sevilla* we're gonna stay at a hotel *y nos vamos a quedar ahí unos cuantos días porque tenemos* **a bank holiday** *¿no?*
 JAYDAN: yes
 NOLAN: a bank holiday on Monday so we're gonna come back on Sunday hopefully and that's gonna be my weekend.
 JAYDAN: **vale**

The most common insertions found in the fourth generation are single Spanish insertions within an otherwise English discourse. This is an interesting phenomenon that is neither related to a lack of proficiency in English nor to a use of culturally and locally established terms. Example (12) presents the insertion of single lexical items related to means of transport, such as *bici* and *moto*, as well as the adverb of place *aquí* meaning “in Gibraltar.” Also striking is the use of Spanish expressions with a strong emotional meaning, including expletives such as

cojones, adjectives such as *amarga(da)*, and fixed expressions like *por la cara*, which belong to oral discourse and are sometimes very commonly used in the Andalusian dialect, a dialect variation that was also noticeable in the pronunciation of these terms.

(12) RG-Corpus: generation 4

MELISSA: but Sarah you have to be careful you can't even ride a bicycle, *ni a bici cojones un puto bici* and you wanna get your *moto aquí*

AROA: no guys it's getting there eh she's getting there I beg

[...]

JENNIFER: I cried in Ryan's house yeah I'm the one that never cries and *por la cara* I ended up crying

SARAH: yeah you and Jeff left and I had to stay with you because you had a *ataque del corazón*

MELISSA: yeah or when we were all sitting down *amarga* on the side and then *bailando* comes on and all of us *bailando*

Also worth noting is the insertion of Spanish lexical items from scientific fields as a way to emphasize a connotation or to reduce the seriousness of the subject, as with *ataque del corazón* in Example (12). Such cases are not very common, but they recall the use of single Spanish insertions as a mechanism related to the identity of younger generations. The relationship with and knowledge of the Spanish culture is also noticeable in the use of Spanish cultural elements such as songs (*bailando*) in Example (12). While older generations make use of a lot of cultural English insertions within Spanish discourse, we observed an extended functionality in the use of Spanish insertions within monolingual English discourse.

4.2 Alternation

Alternation is also a common phenomenon among different generations of Gibraltarian speakers. Speakers from the first and second generations switch from Spanish to English, encompassing grammatical and lexical aspects. In Example (13) from a conversation between speakers from generation I and II, Spanish is the main language of discourse, while there are alternations into English, with several constituents like *really nice* and *I really have*.

(13) FR-Corpus: generation I and II

CUSTOMER: *porque no estaba la muchacha en*

SHOPASSISTANT 1: *Aracel no?*

CUSTOMER: *sí que era suiza pero ahora está el griego porque ella se ha ido*

SHOPASSISTANT 1: *ah se ha ido ya?*

CUSTOMER: *se ha ido por eso yo estaba con ella así con || really nice || pero no yo tengo confidence con este médico*

SHOPASSISTANT 2: *claro*

CUSTOMER: *sí || I really have || no?*

The analyses of generation II show that in comparison to the older generation, they use alternations bidirectionally within a turn, as in Example (14). Long constituents, in this case whole sentences, are switched at major clause boundaries. "As it takes place between utterances in a turn or between turns" (Muysken 2000: 5), this evidences a high proficiency in both languages, which the preceding generation does not always have.

(14) FR-Corpus: generation II

ADRIAN: *El gibraltareño es una persona me gusta decirle latino británico porque somos muy latinos y al mismo tiempo muy británicos también, aunque no lo parecemos no? || We can speak both languages and we understand both cultures and we get the best of both worlds really || no? Ese es el yanito para mi*

Typical alternation patterns also occur in generation III. Once again, we observed bidirectional turns in which sentences in English and Spanish alternate. This code-switching strategy is common within a turn, but it is also commonly observed between interventions. Example (15) exhibits code-switching alternations between turns (as a turn-taking device) and in a turn. Here, Emma, Sophia, and Iris use both English and Spanish to take a turn; finally, Sophia also alternates between languages within her turn. At the beginning of Sophia's long intervention, utterances appear either in English or Spanish, but later there are also some English lexical and grammatical elements (for instance, *single file* or *walking*) within Spanish utterances.

(15) RG-Corpus: generation III

EMMA: *cualquiera sabe*

SOPHIA: we were on two cases now we're up to five again

EMMA: yeah yeah

IRIS: nada

SOPHIA: *pero tú sabes lo que pasa que* || you're allowed in gib to go out || *pero me da un coraje coño* || cause I'm now walking for two hours || *y la gente parece que son tonta coño te ven y ni se meten en un single file o* || they don't they don't make the efforts || *van como como* like a whole family || *como así de nada walking uno al lado de otro pues cojones ponte detrás*

Bidirectional alternation within the third generation is a common code-switching phenomenon in Gibraltar. Here, the use of discourse markers such as *pero*, *y*, or *como* in Example (15) commonly function as triggers for switching into Spanish. By contrast, we did not find a lot of examples of alternation in the youngest generation. In the discourse of the fourth generation, Spanish utterances are usually embedded within English discourses or appear as the result of short responses to speakers, such as *sí*, *se escucha bien* in Example (16). Alternations as repetitions of the same sentence both in English and Spanish—such as *can you hear me? Se escucha?* in Example (16)—are also common.

(16) RG-Corpus: generation IV

ARIANNE: wait can you hear me *bien?* || *Se escucha?*

SUSAN: yes

ALBA: yeah

ARIANNE: okay *vale* cool

SUSAN: *sí se escucha bien*

ALBA: right

SUSAN: but *la verdad que* memories || *cuando Alba nació y me quitó todo el derecho de* || to be fully loved a hundred percent || *que mi madre quiere más a mi hermana que yo*

ALBA: Susan don't say that

SUSAN: *es mentira eh eso es mentira*

As stated above, alternation is not a very common pattern in this generation. However, alternation is common when young speakers refer to other people, especially their parents or grandparents as in Example (16), or directly quote them as in Example (17).

- (17) SUSAN: *no no no* like on a Friday but I remember one day I couldn't sleep and I was like twenty-four hours up and then it was Easter cause dad in the morning was like || "*¿qué quieres vino?*" || and I had the *vino* so basically [I'd basically gone on a sober]
ALBA and ARIANNE: *((laugh))*

4.3 Congruent lexicalization

In this section we look at a combination of items from both languages in one grammatical structure sharing properties of both English and Spanish. This combination is

possible due to a close similarity between the languages involved, which resemble each other in some morphosyntactic and lexical and pragmatic aspects. Example (18) is from a conversation between five men discussing the status of their club.

(18) FR-Corpus: generation I

BRIAN: *porque porque estamos **registered** como un club*

ANDREW: *pero esto no es un club*

PACO: *no es un club we are an association*

BRIAN: I know I know || *somos un association pero estamos registrados como un club*

ERNESTO: *por eso nos cortaron el agua*

RAFAEL: *por eso han cortado el agua*

ERNESTO: *no te extrañe que corten la luz*

Within the verbal periphrasis *estamos registered*, there is a switch. The English participle *registered* is embedded in an otherwise Spanish structure. This is only possible due to the fact that both languages share similar structures. Congruent lexicalization can also be seen in generation II, where the speakers have a relatively high proficiency of Spanish and English. They too lexicalize material from both languages into a shared grammatical structure, as in Example (19).

(19) FR-Corpus: generation II

ALBA: highlight full but each section has its own time limitations

JESSICA: *sí*

ALBA: *eso es muy importante porque yo incluso le sugiero a las mías que hagan el **essay first** cause by the time they get to the essay || *están ya quemadas**

In this example, the Spanish definitive article *el* is followed by the English noun *essay* and the adverb *first*. The sentence structure in this case is the same in Spanish and English, so these types of switches can occur without violating the structure of either language due to the flexibility in the position of the Spanish adverb. The switch back to Spanish *cause by the time they get to the essay están ya quemadas* happens again at a sentence boundary and is thus an illustration of bidirectional alternation.

Congruent lexicalization is present not only in generations I and II but also in generation III. Here again, the use of English participles within verbal periphrasis, such as *tenía [...] planned* in Example (20), allows speakers to find similarities in their bilingual repertoire that trigger the switch. Even though examples of congruent lexicalization are not very common in the RG-Corpus, some of them are noteworthy. One such case is the use of the Spanish adverb *tampoco* in Example (20).

(20) RG-Corpus: generation III

JOHN: *pero tú no tenías ningún holiday **planned** para este verano*

MICKEY: *yo quería ir a Ibiza*

JOHN: *claro y al final no pudimos hacer nada*

NICHOLAS: the big changes of plans obviously *pero **tampoco has been*** a bad summer

Combinations of places followed by the Spanish adverb *ahí* in Example (21) or interesting constructions such as *se ve gente por ahí on bicycles que siempre are out* or *ahí abajo en el muelle lots of people*—both also in Example (21)—do not constitute common examples within the RG-Corpus but represent the individual creativity of speakers. They show how speakers come up with new sentences that share the grammatical properties of both languages and also mix those properties, altering the expected syntactical order of grammatical elements (such as SVO).

(21) RG-Corpus: generation III

SOPHIA: *y gente mayores eh como esta de fifty toda chula por Queens Way ahí corriendo digo*
|| you can tell || *yo de lejos como* || you can tell they can or they can't || *se ve gente on bicycles*
que siempre are out pero fuck it. I've never seen so many people on bikes *y ahí abajo en el*
muelle lots of people.

IRIS: yeah *y aquí en la playa no veas*

Congruent lexicalization is even less common in the fourth generation. A striking exception from Example (22) is when the formation of the past continuous is started in English and followed by the Spanish gerund *rayándome*. In this case, the use of this verb seems to have emotional connotations and is attached to vernacular speech meaning “thinking a lot or getting crazy about something.”

(22) RG-Corpus: generation IV

ARIANNE: I was gonna say something about what were you saying before that? Before the drinking what was it?

SUSAN: mental health

ARIANNE: *ya pero* what about like you need to go out please ehm

SUSAN: that I drunk lots? that I like couldn't sleep? **that I was *rayándome* about** getting to the bea-

As Muysken states, such alternations and congruent lexicalizations are very common if the languages share grammatical structures (L1/L2 matching; Muysken 2013: 714) and are more likely to be bidirectional in comparison to insertions, which tend to be more unidirectional.

4.4 Backflagging

As mentioned above, from generation II onward, but especially in generations III and IV, there are a lot more Spanish insertions in English frames. In these cases, the most common prominent switch is the one defined as backflagging (Muysken 2013). This means that for younger generations, it is not *just* about inserting single lexical items into the other language frame; instead, elements from the heritage language, in this case Spanish, are embedded with grammatical and lexical properties—namely, discourse markers—into the former L2, which is English. As can be deduced from above, this phenomenon was not observed in the first generation (mostly monolingual in Spanish). In generation II, we did note the insertion of discourse markers. These can be single insertions, such as *pero*, or a combination of several discourse markers, like *ah vale es que* in Example (23).

(23) FR-Corpus: generation II

MARTIN: ***pero*** normally I bring something and stay in the building

LILY: yeah but that's what most of us do

MARTIN: ***ah vale es que*** I didn't know what to expect

LILY: that's what most of us do

MARTIN: today being the first day

LILY: most of us do that we just bring a sandwich or we

Backflagging has become a popular code-switching strategy among generations III and IV (Rodríguez García 2024; Rodríguez García and Goría 2023). Discourse markers such as *pero*, *bueno*, and *mira* or response markers like *sí* and *no* appear very frequently in the third generation's speech, as in Example (24), where discourse markers are used to initiate speakers' turns.

- (24) RG-Corpus: generation III
 IRIS: *bueno* can you see the pictures yes or no?
 SOPHIA: I need the picture *joe*⁵
 EMMA: *mira el Juan ahí muerto* || he’s got blood in his head so maybe he was
 IRIS: *no no espérate que* Sophia needs the pictures *espérate espérate* I’m gonna send Sophia the picture oh my god
 EMMA: *vale*

It is also important to mention that discourse markers sometimes trigger or are part of a more significant switch. Especially in the speech of the third generation, there are many examples of Spanish discourse markers appearing at the beginning and end of alternations (Rodríguez García and Goría 2023). We discussed this in the section on alternation with regard to Example (15), in which *pero*, *y*, and *o* appear both at the beginning and at the end of Spanish utterances.

As peripheral elements, Spanish discourse markers are still very present in the speech of younger Gibraltarian generations (Rodríguez García 2022, 2024). Generation IV regularly uses Spanish discourse markers within an otherwise English discourse (Rodríguez García and Goría 2023), as in Example (25). Spanish discourse markers, which in many parts of conversations constitute a whole conversational turn, fulfill discourse and pragmatic motivations that should be broadly studied (see a detailed study of *bueno* in Rodríguez García and Goría 2023). Furthermore, some discourse markers, such as *pero* in Example (25), appear more often in the speech of the fourth generation than in their monolingual counterparts, which makes it even more important to study the changes in functionality and their relationship to individuals’ identities.

- (25) RG-Corpus: generation IV
 ARIANNE: I mean somehow mum would pay for it and then I have to pay her back slowly *pero* like it’s it’s really I think it’s affecting *la verdad que* I think it’s affecting those people
 SUSAN: yeah
 ALBA: how was how was uni like in the- cause you still study *no* Susan?
 SUSAN: yeah me yeah

5. Conclusion (language shift)

To conclude, we argue that Gibraltar represents a case of dilalia and not a classic situation of diglossia (on diglossia, see Ferguson 1959 and Fishman 1967). As we observed in the examples provided for the analysis, the “high variety”, English, is not only used in formal speech, as it was previously, but also in informal settings, while the “low variety”, Spanish, plays a role in informal situations and for social purposes, such as within families, as Monica describes in Example (26).

- (26) FR-Corpus: generation II
 MONICA: my husband and I have lived in the UK for so many years, we naturally speak Sp-English at home. English, we don’t watch Spanish TV but as I said culturally we associate more with the UK than we do with Spain whereas my mum and for instance my dad actually associates a lot with Spain because my grandmother was Spanish. My grandfather, you know, even though he was Gibraltarian, he lived in Spain, grew up in Spain, so whereas I don’t. So the children are brought up, even though they do understand a lot. But their command of the Spanish language isn’t what it was when I was their age, I must admit, and completely our fault, but then again I find it very difficult to, I don’t know to speak at home in Spanish automatically.

⁵ *joe* (Span.) = *joder* (Span.) ~ *damn* (Engl.)

At the center of the linguistic continuum and landscape of Gibraltar, we placed the local variety of code-switching, Yanito. Yanito exhibits how both languages have mixed and entered all speaking environments, reflecting the sociohistorical, political, and linguistic changes of the Gibraltar population. As we showed in the analysis, the structure and meaning of Yanito is different across the different generations. Remarkably, English insertions are most common in the oldest generations, whereas alternations and congruent lexicalizations mostly occur in later generations. The latter pattern can be further distinguished between the generations, as generation II uses Spanish and English as a frame, while English constitutes the matrix in the younger generations. Where Spanish was consistently used within families in the older generation, English has pushed its way into informal contexts and replaced Spanish. At the same time, we can see that there are no clear boundaries. Spanish and English are mixed and used as a common frame, which has finally led to a shift of the matrix language. This shift is manifested from the third generation onward, where English has become the matrix and provides all the grammatical structures (Rodríguez García 2024). Nevertheless, the original language, Spanish, still contributes with grammatical, discursive, and lexical elements in English frames, as has been shown in the case of backflagging (Rodríguez García and Goría 2023). We observed a preference for the use of certain code-switching strategies across different generations of speakers as well as a change in the matrix language of the switch, which reflects a language shift within the community:

		Preferred CS strategy	Matrix language
Generation	I	Insertions	Spanish
	II	Alternations Congruent lexicalization	Spanish/English
	III	Alternations Backflagging	English (Spanish)
	IV	Backflagging Insertions	English

Figure 4: Code-switching strategies and matrix language in Gibraltar generations.

The third generation of speakers was probably the most heterogeneous, and it exhibited stronger individual variation. While some speakers used and combined all the different structural code-switching patterns in their interventions, other speakers showed preferences for the use of English and the insertion of Spanish discourse markers. This individual variation was also present in the fourth generation, but here the preference for the use of backflagging and single Spanish insertions was noticeable and more homogeneous across the speakers. The analysis shows that even though there are common tendencies in the use of code-switching structures, reflecting a language shift across Gibraltar generations, individual variation should still be considered (Rodríguez García 2022).

The investigation also sensed a clear connection between language competence and the type of speaker. Speakers of generation I, who had often spent their whole lifetime in Gibraltar and had a basic level of education, showed a distinctive language competence in Spanish and less in English, especially regarding pronunciation. Generation II—their children so to say—possessed a higher level of education, often having studied abroad, mostly in the UK, some even having lived there for a while, before returning to Gibraltar. This group had a balanced language competence in Spanish and English, while the next generations had a limited proficiency in Spanish and showed less alternation between the two languages. English is not only their mother tongue but also the language at school and with friends. Spanish is often used as a discourse marker embedded in an English frame. There is thus a shift from monolingual

speakers of Spanish to bilingual speakers to almost monolingual English speakers, who, however, use Spanish elements in their speech, which is typical of Yanito in the younger generations (Rodríguez García 2022).

However, not only the use of the languages has shifted from Spanish as the matrix of the first generation to English as the matrix of the youngest generation. The social meaning of the languages has changed as well. The meaning, or the so-called indexical field,⁶ of a language can change over time even if the language remains in the same form: “The same feature receives different social interpretations by (different or same) groups of speakers, in different social and interactional contexts and genres, or different periods of time” (Auer 2013: 201). While for the first generation, the index of belonging, familiarity, and emotional bonding is filled by Spanish, in the next generation, this indexical field is already shared by both languages, Spanish and English, the latter standing for authority, clarity, and order. From the third generation onward, Spanish is no longer the primary language for the index of emotional bonding but is associated with the oldest generation, whom the third generation is emotionally and ethnically related to. In addition, speakers connected Yanito, as the local variety of code-switching and mixing of local Spanish and local English, with local identity and perceived it as a communicative strategy for strengthening the sense of belonging to the community. In a nutshell, through the ability to code-switch, Yanito plays an important role in fostering cohesion within the community. Despite the analyses showing clear generational differences in language use—and even evidence of language shift—the practice of code-switching itself functions as a unifying element. It enables the Gibraltarian linguistic community to negotiate and maintain aspects of its cultural and linguistic identity in the face of external pressures (Rodríguez García 2025).

⁶ Indexical fields are used here with reference to Eckert (2008). She focuses on the social meaning of variation, as meanings of variables are not definite but rather present a range of meanings. She calls this range an indexical field, which is filled with ideologically related meanings that can be individually activated in a specific situation: “Variables have indexical fields rather than fixed meanings because speakers use variables not simply to reflect or reassert their particular pre-ordained place in the social map but to make ideological moves” (Eckert 2008: 464).

References:

- Alameda Hernández, Ángela. 2006. Discursive strategies in the construction of national identity: A critical discourse analysis of the Gibraltar issue in the printed media. *National Identities* 10 (2), 225–235.
- Archer, Edward G. 2006. *Gibraltar: Identity and empire*. New York: Routledge.
- Auer, Peter. 1984. *Bilingual conversation*. John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Auer, Peter. 2005. A postscript: code-switching and social identity. *Journal of Pragmatics* 37(3), 403 – 410.
- Auer, Peter. 2013. *Code-switching in conversation: Language, interaction and identity*. New York: Routledge.
- Canessa, Andrew. 2019. *Bordering on Britishness. National identity in Gibraltar from the Spanish Civil War to Brexit*. Springer International Publishing.
- Eckert, Penelope. 2008. Variation and the indexical field. *Journal of Sociolinguistics* 12 (4), 435-476.
- Errico, Elena. 1997. *Gibraltar: A hybrid of language and culture*. Doctoral Thesis. Università degli Studi di Bologna.
- Escoriza, Morera, Luis & Díaz Hormigo, M. Tadea. 2008. In M. Doppelbauer & P. Cichon (Eds.), *La España multilingüe: lenguas y políticas lingüísticas de España*, 342 – 358. Wien: Praesens Verlag.
- Feijóo Rodríguez, Sonia. 2018. “Somos más British que los British”: *Gibraltar: Code-Switching im Dienst der Identitätskonstruktion*. Doctoral Thesis. Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg.
- Ferguson, Charles. 1959. Diglossia. *Word*, 16, 325 – 340.
- Fishman, Joshua. 1967. Bilingualism with and without diglossia; diglossia with and without bilingualism. *Journal of Social Issues*, 23(2), 29 – 38.
- Gold, Peter. 1994. *A stone in Spain's shoe: the search for a solution to the problem of Gibraltar*. Liverpool University Press.
- Goria, Eugenio. 2018. *Inglese e spagnolo a Gibilterra: Le dinamiche del discorso bilingue*. Caissa Italia.
- Goria, Eugenio. 2020. The road to fusion: The evolution of bilingual speech across three generations of speakers in Gibraltar. *International Journal of Bilingualism* 25 (2), 384 – 400.
- Haller, Dieter. 2000. *Gelebte Grenze Gibraltar. Transnationalismus, Lokalität und Identität in kulturanthropologischer Perspektive*. Wiesbaden: Deutscher Universitäts-Verlag.
- Kellermann, Anja. 2001. *A new New English. Language, politics and identity in Gibraltar*. Norderstedt: Books on Demand GmbH.
- Kramer, Johannes. 1986. *English and Spanish in Gibraltar*. Buske Verlag.
- Krefeld, Thomas. 2004. *Einführung in die Migrationslinguistik: von der ‚Germania italiana‘ in die ‚Romania multipla‘*. Tübingen: Narr.
- Levey, David. 2008. *Language change and variation in Gibraltar*. Amsterdam: Benjamin.
- Moyer, Melissa. 1992. *Analysis of Code Switching in Gibraltar*. Doctoral Thesis. Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona.
- Muysken, Pieter. 2000. *Bilingual speech: a typology of code-mixing*. Cambridge University Press.
- Muysken, Pieter. 2013. Language contact outcomes as the result of bilingual optimization strategies. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition* 16 (4), 709 – 730.
- Myers-Scotton, Carol. 1993. *Duelling Languages: grammatical Structure in Codeswitching*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Rodríguez García, Marta. 2019. *El uso de los marcadores discursivos en el discurso bilingüe gibraltareño*. Master Thesis. New Mexico State University: ProQuest Dissertations Publishing. Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses A&I; ProQuest One

- Literature. (2250246971). Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/el-uso-de-los-marcadores-discursivos-en-discurso/docview/2250246971/se-2?accountid=14616>
- Rodríguez García, Marta. 2022. Hacia una nueva definición del yanito: análisis desde la perspectiva de los jóvenes adultos de Gibraltar. *Boletín Hispánico Helvético* 39-40, 391 – 420.
- Rodríguez García, Marta. 2024. The discursive construction of code-switching in Yanito among the young population of Gibraltar. In Pfadenhauer, Katrin, Serreli, Valentina, Rüdiger Sofia (eds.): *Global and Local Perspective on Language Contact (Contact and Multilingualism)*. Language Science Press.
- Rodríguez García, Marta. 2025. Fronteras porosas: contacto lingüístico y construcción de identidad en Gibraltar. In Bürki, Yvette, García Agüero, Alba Nalleli (eds.): *Language, Borders and Bordering Practices / Lenguaje, fronteras y prácticas de fronterización: Sociolinguistic Perspectives / Perspectivas sociolingüísticas*. De Gruyter.
- Rodríguez García, Marta and Goría, Eugenio. 2023. Backflagging revisited: a case study on *bueno* in English-Spanish bilingual speech. *Journal of Pragmatics* 215, 113 – 130.
- Weston, Daniel. 2013. Code-switching variation in Gibraltar. *International Journal of Bilingualism* 17(1), 3 – 22.